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Research Article

EXPLORING THE CNS-PROTECTIVE ACTIVITY OF NASTURTIUM SATIVUM IN A RAT MODEL OF INDUCED COGNITIVE DEFICIT

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Abstract:

Cognitive deficits are commonly associated with neurodegenerative disorders and are often linked to oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and cholinergic dysfunction. This study aimed to evaluate the central nervous system (CNS)-protective potential of the methanolic extract of Nasturtium sativum seeds in an experimental rat model of cognitive impairment. Cognitive dysfunction was experimentally induced, followed by oral administration of the plant extract in different doses. A standard neuroprotective agent was used as a reference control. Behavioural observations were made to assess learning and memory, and brain tissue was analysed for biochemical markers related to oxidative stress and cholinergic activity. Treatment with the extract showed improvement in cognitive functions and neurochemical parameters, indicating potential CNS-protective effects. The findings suggest that Nasturtium sativum may serve as a promising natural therapeutic agent for managing cognitive disorders due to its neuroprotective and antioxidant properties.

Keyword: Cognitive Deficit, neuroinflammation, oxidative stress, cholinergic dysfunction

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Herbal medicine is the natural system of medicine that has been practiced for more than 5000 years. Ayurveda is a Sanskrit word and its meaning is 'science of life (or) practice of longevity' this system of health care was conceived and developed by the rishis and natural scientists through centuries of observation, discussion, and medication based on trial and error. Herbs are the major components in all indigenous preparations of traditional medicine and a common element in Ayurveda, homeopathic, naturopathic and Native American Indian medicine. Herbal medicine emphasizes prevention of disease; rejuvenation of our body systems and it extends the life span and makes a healthy life in balance and harmony.

From ancient time to the present, people throughout the world have maintained a vast and initiate knowledge of native plants. The plant kingdom has provided innumerable sources of medicinal plants, first used in crude form as herbal teas, syrups, infusions, ointments, liniments and powders. Herbal medicine, sometimes referred as herbalism (or) botanical medicine, is the use of herbs for their therapeutic (or) medicinal value. An herb is a whole plant (or) plant part valued for its medicinal aromatic (or) acceptable qualities. Herbal plants contain variety of chemical substances that act upon the body.

Herbal medicine is the oldest form of health care known to mankind. Herbs have been used by all cultures throughout the history. It was an integral part of the development of modern civilization primitive man observed and appreciated the great diversity of plants available to him. The plant provided food, clothing shelter and medicine. Much of the medicinal use of plants seems to have been developed through observations of wild animals, and by trial and error. As the time went on each tribe added the medicinal power of herbs in their area to its knowledge base. They methodically collected information on herbs and developed well defined herbal pharmacopoeias. The history of herbal medicines is as old as human civilization. The plants were used in the traditional system of medicine practiced in China, Egypt, and Greece long before the beginning of the Christian era.¹⁻⁵

Truly well in to the 20th century much of the pharmacopoeias of scientific medicine were derived from the herbal folklore of native peoples. Many drugs commonly used today are herbal origin. Indeed, about 25 percent of the prescribed drugs dispensed in the United States contain at least one

active ingredient derived from plant material some are made from plant extracts; others are synthesized to mimic a natural plant compound.

The Indian health care science has inherited a large number of traditional practices, systems, medicines as part of its holistic health care scenario, some of them more than 3000 years old. The earliest mention of the medicinal use of plants is to be found in the Rigveda which dates back as early as 3500 BC. It is Ayurveda, the Atharvaveda, is considered to be the ancient medical science of India. Natural product is a single chemical containing compound that occurs naturally. This term is typically used to refer to an organic compound of limited distribution in nature (often called secondary metabolites). Natural products have been a major source of drugs for centuries. With more than 25% of the pharmaceuticals in daily use of today's are derived from natural products, so therefore interest in natural products research remains strong [5-6].

This is belonging to several factors, including unmet therapeutic needs that compel new drug discovery, the remarkable diversity of both chemical structures and biological activities of naturally occurring secondary metabolites, the utility of bio-active natural products as biochemical and chemical probes, the development of novel and sensitive techniques to detect biologically active natural products, improved techniques to isolate, purify, and structurally characterize these active constituents, advances in solving the demand for bulk supply of complex Natural products, and the success of herbal remedies in the global market place.

With the advancement of the chemistry and western medicine, the active substances of many species have been isolated and utilized. According to WHO estimation 80% of world population presently uses the herbal medicine for specific primary health care; about 25% of the prescription drugs dispensed to us contain at least one active ingredient of plant origin. Laboratorial and clinical investigation on herbal preparations and other therapies shows that they have a various range of potential results for treating infectious diseases, diabetes and promoting health. Mechanisms underlying these effects may comprise free radical scavenging, brain neurotransmitter modulation and hormonal effects.

The present specified direction is to replace the crude plants with the pure active principles has been started with the investigating work in 18th century by isolating organic acids from plants. The active constituents from plants have been curing off the

elements with less threat of adverse reactions. The synthetic preparations of some drugs are either unknown (or) economically impractical. So for these reasons scientists are continuing to search for and test little known plants and conserve those medicinal properties which have become critical in fight against diseases. Extremely large opportunities exist for multi-disciplinary research that joins the forces of pharmacognosy and natural products chemistry, molecular and cellular biology, medicinal and analytical chemistry, biochemistry, pharmacology and pharmaceuticals to exploit the vast diversity of chemical structures and biological activities of Natural products. etc.

Ayurveda – ancient science of life is believed to be prevalent for last 5000 years in India. It is one of the oldest systems of medicine in the world. Ayurveda is based on hypothesis that everything in the universe is composed of five basic elements viz. space, air, energy, liquid and solid. They exist in the human body in combined forms like vata (space & air); pita and kapha together are called tridosha (three pillars of life).

NEURODEGENERATION

Oxidative stress is to be involved as one of the primary factors that contribute to the development of neurodegenerative diseases like, Alzheimer's, Parkinsonism and neurological conditions like brain damage, epileptic seizures, stroke, neurotrauma, hypoxia etc;

Morphological, biochemical and molecular studies which are undertaken in the recent years both in experimental animals and in man have shown that oxidative stress plays a fundamental role in the development of degenerative changes in cells and tissues of our body. The highest degree of oxidative damage usually occurs in organs like brain, heart and skeletal muscles, since these organs are composed primarily of post mitotic cells. The central nervous system shows increased susceptibility to oxidative stress because of its high oxygen consumption rate (20% of the total oxygen inhaled by the body) that accounts for the increase in generation of oxygen free radicals and reactive oxygen substances like superoxide radical (O_2^-), single oxygen (O_2), H_2O_2 and hydroxyl radical (OH).

During this stage all the cells and tissues of our body are also equipped with anti-oxidative enzymes like super oxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GPX), glutathione reductase (GRD) and substances like reduced glutathione (GSH). They dispose the free radicals as and when they are generated thereby

protecting the cells and tissues from the oxidative harms. Generally, the balance is maintained between the oxidative attack of the free radicals and the anti-oxidative defence system existing in the cells and tissues of our body.[6-9]

Several series of stages disturb this balance by increasing the formation of free radicals in comparatively to the available oxidants (thus, oxidative stress), example of free radical formation, immune cell activation, inflammation ischemia, infection, cancer and so on, free radicals and the effect of these toxic molecules on cell function (which can result in cell death) known as oxidative stress. These free radicals are highly reactive, unstable molecules thus unpaired electron in their outer most shells. They react with (oxidize) various cellular components and free radicals lead to DNA damage, mitochondrial dysfunction, cell membrane damage, and eventually cell death (Apoptosis-which is called as cell death) [10-12].

Brain has a low level of anti-oxidative defence system. The concentration of various anti-oxidant enzymes like SOD, GPX, GRD, catalase, is low in the brain. The glutathione (GSH) concentration is also very much reduced in the brain when compared to other organs in the body. In addition to these factors brain has high iron and ascorbate content in the certain region, which provides favourable conditions for generation of oxygen free radicals.[13-14]

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Preparation of the Extract

The collected *Nasturtium sativum* are washed, air dried, homogenized to fine powder and stored in airtight bottles. Dried powder will first defat with petroleum ether and then extracted with Ethanol by using the Soxhlet apparatus.

Extraction procedure

Coarsely powdered *Nasturtium sativum* plant were used for extraction with Ethanol by using Soxhlet method for 6-8 hours. 25g of dried powder was weighed and 200mL of solvent Ethanol is used for the extraction. The extracts were evaporated by using a rotary evaporator and dried at room temperature. The obtained crude extracts were weighed and stored at 4°C for further analysis. [15]

EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS

Colony inbred strains of Wister rats of either sex weighing 200-220g were used for the pharmacological studies. The animals were kept under standard conditions (day/night rhythm) 8.00

am to 8.00 p.m., $22 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ room temperature, in polypropylene cages. The animals were fed on a standard pelleted diet and water ad libitum. The animals were housed for one week in polypropylene cages before the experiments to accustomize to laboratory conditions. It is randomly distributed into four different groups with six animals in each group under identical conditions throughout the experiments. The experimental protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC) of CCSEA (Committee for Control and Supervision of Experimental Animals).

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN [16]

The animals were divided into 5 groups of 6 rats each as follows:

Group I- served as control and received normal saline. (Normal control)

Group II- served as hypoxic rats and received sodium nitrite water for 14 days. (Hypoxic control)

Group III- animals received standard drug Dextromethorphan and sodium nitrite water for 14 days. (Standard drug control)

Group IV- animals received *Nasturtium sativum* suspended in 1% gum acacia and sodium nitrite water for 14 days.

Group V- animals received *Nasturtium sativum* suspended in 1% gum acacia and sodium nitrite water for 14 days.

Induction of Neurodegeneration

Drug administration Scopolamine-induced memory impairment model was validated by clinically used nootropic agent Dextromethorphan. It was administered at a dose of 100 mg/kg, i.p. for 1 week. The EENS and CM seed oil were uniformly suspended in 1% carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) dissolved in water and administered orally (p.o.). They were administered at doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg for 1 week. The group administered with CMC (10 mL/kg, p.o.) for 1 week and normal saline (i.p.) on last days served as the vehicle group. 1 hr after the administration of vehicle or *Nasturtium sativum* or extracts, the scopolamine was injected to induce memory impairment in rats⁵².

Elevated Plus Maze

The elevated plus maze served as the exteroceptive behavioural model (wherein the stimulus existed outside the body) to evaluate learning and memory in mice. The apparatus consisted of two open arms (16 cm x 5 cm) and two covered arms (16 cm x 5 cm x 12 cm). The arms extended from a central platform (5 cm x 5 cm), and maze was elevated to a height of 25 cm from the floor. On the first day, each animal was placed at the end of open arm, facing away from the

central platform. Transfer latency (TL) was taken as the time taken by animal to move into one of the covered arm with all its four legs. TL was recorded on the first day. If the animal did not enter into one of the covered arm within 90 s, it was gently pushed into one of the two covered arms and the TL was assigned as 90 s. The animal was allowed to explore the maze for 10 s and then returned to its home cage. Memory retention was examined 24 h after the first day trial on the second day.

Acetylcholinesterase activity in Cortex, Cerebellum and Hippocampus [17]

Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) is a serine protease that hydrolyses the neurotransmitter acetylcholine. AChE is found at mainly neuromuscular junctions and cholinergic brain synapses, where its activity serves to terminate synaptic transmission. It belongs to carboxyl esterase family of enzymes.

Principle of Assay

Acetylcholinesterase assay is based on an Ellman method, in which thiocholine produced by the action of acetylcholinesterase forms a yellow Colour with 5, 5'-dithiobis (2-nitrobenzoic acid). The intensity of the product Colour, measured at 412 nm, is proportionate to the enzyme activity in the sample.

Procedure

The brain homogenate in a volume of 500 μL was mixed with 1% Triton X-100 and centrifuged at $10,000 \times g$ at 4°C for 60 min. Supernatant was collected and used for acetylcholinesterase (AChE) estimation. The assay mixture contained 0.4 ml of supernatant, 2.4 ml phosphate buffer (pH 8), 20 μl of acetylthiocholine iodide and 100 μl of DTNB. The change in absorbance was measured for 10 min at 2 min interval at 412 nm using spectrophotometer. The activity of AChE was expressed in $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$ of protein.

The specific activity of AChE was calculated by following formula:

$$\text{AChE activity} = \Delta E \times 1000 \times V / 1.36 \times 10000 \times v$$

ΔE = Extinction change/min

1000 = Conversion factor for μmoles

V = Volume of the total reaction mixture

1.36×10000 = Extinction Coefficient

v = volume of the enzyme (supernatant) used

One unit of acetylcholinesterase activity was defined as the number of micromoles of acetylthiocholine iodide hydrolysed per minute per milligram of protein. The specific activity of acetylcholinesterase is expressed in $\mu\text{moles}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$ protein.

Estimation of acetylcholinesterase enzyme levels in the brain [18]

All the groups showed attenuate acetylcholinesterase accelerator activity as compared with scopolamine, as indicative. The acetyl enzyme activity was considerably hyperbolic by scopolamine as compared to the control group. The rise in AChE activity by scopolamine was considerably reduced by drug-

treated groups. High dose animals showed a vital decrease in acyl-enzyme activity compared with low and medium dose, whereas extract only group showed a vital decrease in acetylcholinesterase activity compared with medium and low. The decrease in a acetylcholinesterase enzyme activity showed improvement in memory and provides anti-Alzheimer's activity.

3. RESULTS:

Table Effect of ethanolic leaves extract of *Nasturtium sativum* acetylcholine esterase level

Groups	Acetylcholine esterase level
Group I (Control group)	0.0824 ± 0.001
Group II (scopolamine (0.3 mg/Kg))	0.107 ± 0.001
Group III (scopolamine + Dextromethorphan (100 mg/kg))	0.078 ± 0.00115
Group IV (scopolamine + EENS, 100 mg/kg)	0.085 ± 0.0025
Group V (scopolamine + EENS, 200 mg/kg)	0.081 ± 0.0001

Values are expressed as the mean ± standard error of mean of n=6 rats/treatment. Significance **p≤0.01

Effect of *Nasturtium sativum* scopolamine-induced memory impairment in Elevated plus maze test

The impact of all the drug-treated groups was evaluated at the top of 14th day. TL was recorded. It absolutely was seen that TL for all the drug-treated groups was less on the 15th day as compared to the 14th day. Decrease IR indicates the induction of a state of mind, and exaggerated IR indicates in improvement in psychological features and memory impairment. Negative control group (scopolamine) animals were considerably shrunken compared with all the groups that indicated that state of mind is evoked. Furthermore, high dose showed an increase in IR compared with intermediate and low dose separately and also the extract the only group showed significant increase compared with the negative group.

Table: Effect of Effect of ethanolic leaves extract of *Nasturtium sativum*

Groups	IR	TL Day: 14	TL Day: 15
Group I (Control group)	0.683 ± 0.068	18.223	9.5
Group II (scopolamine (0.3 mg/Kg))	0.582 ± 0.115	38.45	27.69
Group III (scopolamine + Dextromethorphan (100 mg/kg))	0.789 ± 0.075	26.27	14.14
Group IV (scopolamine + EENS, 100 mg/kg)	0.598 ± 0.046	29.46	17.6
Group V (scopolamine + EENS, 200 mg/kg)	0.623 ± 0.121	26	19.13

Values are expressed as the mean ± standard error of mean of n = 6 rats/treatment. Significance **p≤0.01. TL: Transfer latency, IR: Inflexion ratio

4. DISCUSSION:

The present study aimed to evaluate the central nervous system (CNS)-protective and nootropic potential of *Nasturtium sativum* in a scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit model in rats. Scopolamine, a muscarinic acetylcholine receptor antagonist, is widely used to induce cognitive dysfunction by impairing cholinergic neurotransmission, thus mimicking Alzheimer's disease-like symptoms. In this model, dextromethorphan was used as the standard reference drug due to its known neuroprotective and anti-glutamatergic properties. Behavioural and biochemical assessments were performed using the Elevated Plus Maze (EPM) and acetylcholinesterase (AChE) enzyme activity in the rat brain.

Behavioural Assessment – Elevated Plus Maze (EPM):

In the EPM test, scopolamine-treated rats exhibited significantly increased transfer latency (TL), indicating impaired learning and memory. Treatment with *Nasturtium sativum* significantly reduced TL compared to the negative control, suggesting an improvement in spatial learning and memory. These effects were comparable to the standard drug dextromethorphan, indicating that *Nasturtium sativum* may exert beneficial effects on cognition. Biochemical Analysis – Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) Activity: scopolamine administration led to a significant elevation in AChE activity in brain tissue, reflective of increased breakdown of acetylcholine and cholinergic dysfunction. However, treatment with *Nasturtium sativum* markedly decreased AChE activity, suggesting enhancement of cholinergic transmission and a protective effect on cholinergic

neurons. This aligns with the observed behavioural improvements and supports the potential role of *Nasturtium sativum* as a cholinergic enhancer.

Possible Mechanisms:

The observed CNS-protective effects of *Nasturtium sativum* may be attributed to:

- Antioxidant activity (as suggested by previous phytochemical studies)
- Anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective effects
- Modulation of cholinergic neurotransmission via AChE inhibition

5. CONCLUSION:

The findings from both behavioural and biochemical parameters suggest that *Nasturtium sativum* possesses significant nootropic and neuroprotective activity in a scopolamine-induced cognitive deficit model. Its effect is likely mediated through acetylcholine esterase inhibition and restoration of cholinergic function, similar to the action of dextromethorphan. Further studies are warranted to isolate active constituents and explore molecular pathways involved in its neuroprotective activity.

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